

THE METHODOLOGY OF USING DICTIONARIES IN LANGUAGE LESSONS IN A SECONDARY SCHOOL SETTING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14465695>

Abstract. Article discusses the problem of using all types of English dictionaries at the language classes in a secondary school setting, such as bilingual, monolingual, British English and American English dictionaries which all play different roles in secondary education where foreign languages are taught and its results are presented.

Keywords: methodology, dictionary, lexical, bilingual, monolingual pronunciation, electronic dictionaries.

Introduction

Dictionaries are considered one of the most significant means which are used in learning English. These resources not only help with understanding the meaning of new words but also assist in expanding students’ vocabulary and also their pronunciation, enhancing their familiarity with the language. The correct use of dictionaries helps to improve language skills and makes independent learning easier for students in a secondary setting. There are many types of dictionaries such as monolingual, bilingual, electronic dictionaries which are intended for first language users which defines words in that language. The bilingual dictionaries for second language users which is written in both first and second languages of the user, with translations from either language to the other. According to Kharisov and Kharisova (2014[2730;6]) are analysed the importance of dictionaries in teaching, and enhancing vocabulary, translation skills and also discussed advantages of printed and paper based dictionaries.

According to Gregory and Lowen, (1999)[4;5] opines that Dictionaries are instruments of lifelong learning, it is to them that we turn to revive our second language skills and to enhance our native vocabulary. According to Grinshtain (2014) e-dictionaries is highly recommended to use. In addition, printed one is also helpful and in cannot keep up with the dynamic change changes in the language. According to Aleeva and Safullina (2016)[5;1], English and Tatar language Dictionary for learners is based on the role of bilingual dictionaries. In addition, for secondary school students, it is recommended to use both paper dictionaries and also electronic dictionaries. For instance, more learners nowadays are using more electronic dictionaries than paper dictionaries. Nurmuhammedov identifies six online dictionaries for students such as learners follow: the Cambridge learner’s dictionary, Cambridge Advanced learner’s Dictionary, Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English, Macmillian Dictionary. The functions of these dictionaries are essentially to define meaning of words, pronunciation, spelling, show syllabication, abbreviations translations and usage. Moreover, it is presented table where we can see the differences of American and British dictionaries, how to use its pronunciation:

Aspects	British English	American English
Spelling	Colour, favour, centre	Color, favor, center
Lexical difference	Boot (,trunk), flat(apartment), holiday	Trunk, apartment, vacation
Pronunciation	Mostly sound “r” is not pronounced (for ex. car)	“r” is pronounced fully
Grammar	Mostly Present perfect is	

	used I've just eaten	
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In my opinion, we can see how words are pronounced and also its pronunciation, lexical difference in American English and British English. Moreover, we have known its usage in English lessons. Some of the scientists and linguists focused on monolingual, electronic, bilingual dictionaries and its usage in secondary schools. But in my opinion, teachers should encourage students during reading writing and language exercises to work independently not relying on dictionaries every word in the context. While teaching students mustn't rely on dictionaries to understand every word in contexts in the sentences should stop writing down the translation of new words without thinking about it just look their real meaning or how they are used in a sentence. They just look a monolingual dictionaries it is known as a reference resources. If students want to a description they should just repeat the same adjectives and find some other options in a dictionary. If students want to find out about how adjectives are usually ordered in English they should just look a grammar reference book.

Conclusion:

To sum up, using of all types dictionaries in language lessons at secondary school setting is highly effective methodology for enhancing students' language skills. It promotes vocabulary development, improves pronunciation and spelling and focus on independent learning and serves as a significant tool that support students' linguistic growth. Moreover, each type of dictionary has its pros and cons. And it depends on how one combines the use of electronic and printed dictionaries in teaching and mastering English as a foreign language. dictionaries saves a lot of time, because words are found in a second, besides it provides pronunciation of words recommended to use. In addition, printed one is also helpful and in can not keep up with the dynamic change changes in the language and also students will enjoy using them, become comfortable with them as a learning resource.

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